

Matters Arising: Marchitelli *et al.* (2020) On the correlation between solar activity and large earthquakes worldwide. *Sci Rep* 10:11495

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Abstract. Quoting late Professor Aaron Levenstein, statistics are like a bikini or a pair of Speedos; what they reveal is suggestive, but what they conceal is vital. In the language of natural sciences, statistics of macroscopic phenomena can reveal nothing about macroscopic physics. Nevertheless, in their statistics-only study on correlations of two data sets, the authors of [1] claimed a global (seismogenic) physical mechanism no less. Besides, their study was flawed from the outset: while preparing the event data set to compare it statistically against the occurrences of some solar events, the authors chose not to decluster, claiming “declustering would result in a completely uncorrelated catalogue, likely destroying key information they were looking for.” This approach was critically wrong from both statistics and physics points of view.

Key words: seismogenesis, tectonogenesis, wily statistics, resonance tectonics, tidally generated seismicity, magnifying mechanical oscillators.

Quoting late Professor Aaron Levenstein, *statistics are like a bikini or a pair of Speedos; what they reveal is suggestive, but what they conceal is vital.* In the language of natural sciences, statistics of macroscopic phenomena can reveal nothing about macroscopic physics. Nevertheless, in their statistics-only study on correlations of two data sets, the authors of [1] claimed a global (seismogenic) physical mechanism no less. Besides, their study was flawed from the outset: while preparing the event data set to compare it statistically against the occurrences of some solar events, the authors chose not to decluster their event data set, claiming “declustering would result in a completely uncorrelated catalogue, likely destroying key information they were looking for.”

From the physics point of view, this approach to data preparation only is justified if it is known that the inner correlation of an event data set is entirely due to an underlying common seismogenic physical mechanism that is therefore guaranteed to drive (apply to) both global- and local-scale seismicity. However, the authors did not know this. According to them, no such seismogenic physical mechanism and its inner workings are known. Even from the statistics point of view alone, clustering introduces a bias due to the failure to ensure proper sample randomization; the flaws in the sample selection lead to some elements or groups of elements being less likely to be included in the sample. The bias distorts statistical analyses of a sample and affects the statistical significance of statistical tests; besides, the statistical parameter is overstated or understated, and so is never representative of the entire population. [2][3][4] Worse yet, the authors confused the sampling errors (from non-random sampling, here cluster-sampling) for a physical mechanism (here of Sun particles allegedly inducing Earth's M5.6+ strong seismicity).

So not only did the authors fail to offer a physical mechanism to support the claim that Sun causes (any) earthquakes, but the statistics they performed did not represent the overall seismic process, was biased and erroneous, and thus fundamentally flawed even from the statistics point of view. Besides, sampling errors themselves have no meaning outside statistics, and therefore no physical meaning either; thus, they cannot be used – in whatever fashion – to draw additional physical meanings either. The authors' (statistical) result is statistically dubious and physically useless. No physical meaning to their M5.6 cutoff-magnitude was given either. While the statistical justification claimed that the sample size is thus largest, they did not even look into tradeoff of

changing the sample size to make the data set representative of a (global seismogenic) physical mechanism – of which they admit they know nothing at that.

Contrary to the claim that generalized evidence for a tidal component in earthquake activity has never been proven, such evidence has been found recently from Mw5.6+ seismicity on Earth [5], as well as proven temporally- and spatially-independently from moonquakes [6][7][8], thus revealing mechanistic tectonics as the universal seismogenic mechanism (of mechanical resonance magnification) due to the gravitational vector's stirring of the rotating mass. This mechanism is further substantiated by the absolute generalization of the universal mechanism, resulting in the only known analytical relationship between the common physical proportionalities G (and thus gravity too) and c [9][10], while for the first time relating physics at macroscopic and quantum scales – in a dire clash with Einstein's general relativity theory [11]. [5-6] also showed that declustering improves spectral resolution and computations of $M_w5.6+$ seismicity occurrences, as expected of genuine seismogenic physical mechanisms.

Akin to studies investigating temporal correlations between ionospheric total electron content and seismicity, the authors in their study took "electrical seismicity" to be a proven concept, but this is not the case. Namely, such studies reveal that (A) electrical and other phenomena sometimes co-occur with earthquakes, but also that (B) in the majority of strong earthquakes such phenomena are absent altogether. This revelation only suggests that those phenomena could be a byproduct of the seismogenic physical mechanism as it prepares the Earth's solids and gasses (including the atmosphere and magnetosphere) for rupture that we call earthquake, but nothing more. "Electrical seismicity" or *atmoquakes* are part of the same mechanism which is responsible for strong earthquakes. Besides, cluster-sampling that is inherently biased and erroneous across an entire data set cannot be used to examine and discard/support (A) or (B) or both.

This incessant physical mechanism – which arises by way of the gravitational vector's grinding against rotating bodies of mass – makes for a secondary gravitational effect that in nature increases system energetics by 100s of times, as well as produces said accompanying electrical phenomena including planetary magnetic fields as an associated feature of a mechanical oscillator. [12] The authors' study is speculative at best (not qualitative as they misnamed it); for example, the authors used "could" and "can" 27 times v. "may" and "might" 3 times. A correlation between solar activity and global seismicity *definitely* was not definitively established.

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